

**HYBRID APPROACH TO AN AUTOMATED
CHAIN GRAPH CONSTRUCTION**

Taghi Aliyev

Master Thesis 16-17

THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT
OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF
MASTER OF SCIENCE OF OPERATIONS RESEARCH
AT THE FACULTY OF HUMANITIES AND SCIENCES
OF MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY

Thesis committee:

Dr. Joël Karel
Dr. Evgueni Smirnov
Marco Manca, MD
Prof. Dr. Ir. Eric Biessens

Maastricht University
Department of Knowledge Engineering
Maastricht, The Netherlands
August 2016

Preface

This master thesis is written in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Science of Operations Research at the Department of Data Science and Knowledge Engineering. This thesis is placed within the field of modeling of complex systems in medicine, specifically the modeling of inter-relations of multiple *-omics* data.

I would like to thank my thesis supervisors Dr. Joël Karel, Dr. Evgueni Smirnov, MD Marco Manca and Prof. Dr. Ir. Eric Biessens, for their insight, knowledge and above all tolerance for discussions we had. Additionally, I would like to send my gratitude to the whole DKE staff, for their unconditional help, mentorship and for becoming like a second family to me. I would also like to thank Dries de Rydt, Gijs-Jan Roelofs, Bas Willemse, Dennis Soemers, Ramy Al Sharif, Toghrol Bayramov, Berk Isikal and other friends who went through my endless talks on the subjects within this thesis and above. Finally but certainly not least, I would like to thank my family for their unconditional support during my education at DKE. I always felt your support even though you were far away.

Summary

Structural Learning of Graphical Models within the field of Bioinformatics has gained a large attraction recently. The shortage of the literature and available software for learning and integrating multi *-omics* data into a single chain graph, makes them a rather unpopular approach. Chain Graph's power lies in its versatility in modeling the relations, as well as its characteristics especially in the case of dealing with multi *-omics* data.

In order to contribute to the field, a hybrid approach combining multiple different algorithms is proposed. This approach tries to make use of the best of different worlds in order to overcome a single problem of automated chain graph learning. The approach includes techniques like Glasso algorithm for Undirected Independence Graph estimation, Skeleton Recovery Algorithm that makes use of the tree decompositions and Additive Noise Models that are used for distinguishing effect from a cause within observational data.

The power and the correctness of the approach is tested on two types of data sets. First experiments apply the hybrid approach on a data gathered from different weather stations in Germany in years 1969-1990. One fact that made this data set more attractive is the ease of validity of the model. After showing the positive results obtained from first experiments, hybrid approach is further applied on medical data sets of large size. In this case, validating the model is a tough task, and was only done partially on small subsets.

High recall and precision rates obtained in non-medical experiments showed the power of this hybrid approach as an option to automatically model data sets as a chain graph. However, experiments regarding the medical data sets should be further revised. Without an availability of a data set with larger number of samples, it is impossible to validate the approach on medical case. At last, results can be parsed in order to generate new hypothesis that could lead to new discoveries once the model and input is fixed.

Contents

Preface	iii
Summary	v
Contents	vii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Graphical Models	2
1.2 Problem Statement and Research Questions	2
1.2.1 Research Questions	3
1.3 Thesis outline	3
2 Data	5
2.1 Weather Stations Data	5
2.2 Medical Data	6
2.3 Summary	7
3 Graphical Models and Definitions	9
3.1 Background	9
3.2 Terminology	10
3.2.1 Separation Trees	11
3.3 Summary	12
4 Chain Graph Construction	13
4.1 Skeleton Recovery	14
4.2 Undirected Independence Graph	16
4.2.1 Glasso Algorithm	16
4.3 Additive Noise Models	18
4.3.1 HSIC score	20
4.4 Summary	21
5 Experiments and Results	23
5.1 Experimental Setup	23
5.2 Results	24
5.2.1 Weather station data	24
5.2.2 Multi <i>-omics</i> data	25
5.3 Summary	28
6 Conclusion and Future Work	31
6.1 Research Questions	31
6.2 Problem Statement	32
6.3 Future Work	32

Introduction

“A theory has only the alternative of being right or wrong. A model has a third possibility: it may be right, but irrelevant.”

– Manfred Eigen

Chapter overview: *The following chapter introduces the reader to the main topic of the research and also determines the research questions that will be investigated within this thesis.*

In the past decade, advances and availability of a number of new high-throughput technologies allowed for the characterisation of the multi-leveled molecular phenotypes (so called *-omics* data). This, in its turn, provided an opportunity for in-depth characterisation of human physiological processes. With the availability of newer technology, also came sheer volumes of data. On one hand, this sheer volume of data offers the unique opportunity to study how individual parts of a biological system work together to produce complex phenotypes. The ambitious goal of the post-genomic era is indeed the understanding of an entire biological system by modelling, predicting, and controlling the behaviour of all its components. On the other hand, the complexity of available data makes it necessary to develop new computational methods to assist with their integration.

One crucial aspect in the development of the new methods, is the choice of the model. An appropriate model allows a researcher to better formulate the problem, the domain of interest and to simplify the complexity of the system through precise definitions and to dissect the role of each component, for instance by means of system simulations [18]. In systems biology the usage of integrative approaches to study the function of biological systems and to emphasise the importance of a holistic view is widely adopted. The knowledge of the wiring and interplay of these individual parts is a mandatory step to understand complex properties and functionalities of a biological system. In last decades, development of reductionist approaches, aiming at understanding a system one component a time, have been effective in explaining the basis of numerous living processes. However, they are actually inadequate to completely describe biological systems by themselves [3].

In this thesis, Chain Graph models [21] are proposed to be used as a main representation of *-omics* data. Chain Graphs (CG) are a class of Probabilistic Graph Models (PGMs) and can be seen as a unification and generalisation of Bayesian and Markov networks. They were first introduced by Lauritzen, Wermuth and Frydenberg in their seminal works [12, 36, 20].

Main novelty introduced within this thesis is the creation of the hybrid approach, which combines different methods, and breaks the larger structural learning problem into smaller tasks, which are then solved using methods that are known to perform well within their domains. Research done so far on structural learning of the chain graphs only focused on singular methods that tried to solve the whole problem. Some of those approaches even required a manual labor in order to achieve the end goal of estimating CG. In the proposed approach, manual labor is reduced to minimum. Additionally, such an approach allows for the optimization of the well-separated parts of the proposed approach in future.

1.1 Graphical Models

In recent years, many researchers attempted to model the components of a whole biological system separately from each other (*Reductionist approach*). To do so, models and methods like Bayesian Networks [25], Markov Chains/Networks [33], Weighted Gene Co-expression Analysis (WGCNA) [19] and many other have been used. However, there have not been much work done on integration of multiple *-omics* data till recently [6].

Compared to other techniques, what makes CG a promising formalism in systems biology and modelling of biological systems is its characteristics. First, CGs allow one to codify systems as interacting blocks, and in biological systems omics data, each of them defining a block, interacts with one another according to a well-established flow of information. For instance, DNA variations (a block of explanatory variable) can influence complex traits (the block of response variable) through modification of the protein sequence (another block of explanatory variables), or these influences can be mediated through other factors, such as gene expressions (explanatory variables). Second, CGs model interactions within blocks, and interactions within omics are also present. For instance, alleles at Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) that are close to each other can show correlation through linkage disequilibrium, genes belonging to the same pathway interact, and some phenotypes may be under the influence of other phenotypes, for example, Body Mass Index (BMI), which affects the risk of cardiovascular diseases and type 2 diabetes (Figure 1.1(a)). One thing to note here is that, the second characteristic of CGs is not used in the hybrid approach explained below. Third, CGs are flexible and allow the integration of any new class of data simply by adding a new block in the dependence chain. Therefore additional omics data, such as metabolomics data or measured environmental variables, can be easily integrated in the model (Figure 1.1(b)).

Figure 1.1: Two examples of chain graphs representing the interactions within a biological system.

1.2 Problem Statement and Research Questions

Application of Chain Graphs in Systems Biology is not completely new. Several studies [9, 23] have already made use of CGs in order to model their patient data. Results shown in those papers, proved the applicability of CGs, however they are limited to small data sets. In fact, there are two problems related to the size of the model. First, each block may include tens of thousands variables (and hundreds of thousands of relationships) entailing a huge parameter space and difficult computational problems. For instance, the exact solution to the problem of inference over a MN involves a computational complexity that grows exponentially with the size of the maximal clique in the network. On the other hand, there are practical difficulties concerning the estimation of a large number of parameters from data. Indeed, the number of variables (and of relationships) to model is several orders of magnitude larger than the number of subjects (independent measurements) available in human cohorts.

Thus, the **problem statement** of this thesis is:

How can Chain Graphs be made easily applicable in multi -omics integration projects?

1.2.1 Research Questions

One interesting aspect of the CG estimation is the decision/prediction of relations within and in-between data sets. Computationally, deciding which edges should be in the graph is one of the most important questions to answer. In that regard, some methods are available in order to construct a skeleton of a graph. However, they have only been tested as a stand-alone tools. This leads to a following research question:

1. *How accurate is the skeleton recovery algorithm when combined with different approaches?*

The Skeleton Recovery Algorithm, also provides an option for guessing which edges should be directional through complex recovery approach [39]. However, in our models, the edges that should be directed are already known. This basically comes from the model assumption we made. In CG, directed edges only exist in-between blocks, meaning, if skeleton contains an edge where two vertices are from different domains, then the edge should be directed. Several algorithms are known to be able to predict the causality from observational data. This, in its turn, leads to two more research questions:

2. *How different are the models obtained from stand-alone Skeleton Recovery Algorithm and Additive Noise Model (ANM) combined model?*
3. *How well does ANM predict the directions of the edges when combined with Skeleton Recovery Algorithm?*

Considering the facts mentioned in the previous subsection, main focus of this thesis is the generation of CG models of a given data set. To achieve this goal, a hybrid approach consisting of Graphical Lasso regression [11] using Stability Approach to Regularization Selection (StaRS), Skeleton Recovery Algorithm [39] and Additive Noise Models (ANM) [24] is proposed. Details of each individual part of overall flow of the algorithm is described in **Chapter 4**.

1.3 Thesis outline

Thesis starts with an introduction to the problem at hand and proposed solution/approach to it. **Chapter 2** describes the different data sets used for experiments. **Chapter 3** generalizes different graphical models and gives more in-depth explanation to Chain Graphs (CG). **Chapter 4** focuses on the parts of the hybrid approach and explains the computations behind each algorithm. **Chapter 5** provides the information regarding the experimental setup and link between data sets explained in Chapter 2 and algorithms explained in Chapter 4. **Chapter 6** shows the results of these experiments and possible power of the proposed approach. **Chapter 7 and 8** concludes the thesis and provides relevant future work and possible enhancements of the algorithms. Each chapter, except for Introduction and Conclusion chapters, also contains a small summary section at the end wrapping the important points described in the chapter.

2

Data

Chapter overview: *The following chapter describes the origins and structure of the datasets used in this thesis. Datasets are distinguished into two groups: 1. Weather Stations data set 2. Medical, real-world Datasets.*

The proposed hybrid approach and its parts need to be tested and validated with different type of datasets. Mainly, two types of experiments are carried out for each of the algorithms. First, methods are validated from functional perspective by means of non-medical data sets. Afterwards, real-world data matrices are used in order to assess the power of proposed approach.

2.1 Weather Stations Data

In order to test the functionality of the methods and their integration together, first hybrid approach was tested on non-medical data. One such data set used for experiments consisted of measurements from 349 weather stations in Germany. Dataset is provided by the Deutscher Wetterdienst and can be found on <http://www.dwd.de>. Data set contains information about measured temperature, longitude, altitude, latitude, precipitation levels and duration of sunshine. One characteristic of a data set that makes it suitable for our experiments is the availability of a ground truth. Facts like altitude affecting temperature is quite straight-forward and is a settled fact. As, this kind of "clear and obvious" relations are not easily available in case of medical data sets, it makes sense to first check the approach by feeding a simpler approach.

Same dataset was used in [24], where they tested the power of their ANM approach. However, they only focused on bivariate cases, rather than trying to see which connections pop-up from the merged data set. In our experiments, all the variables are combined into a single data matrix and additionally, random effects are added to the matrix as well (Such as adding features with uniformly distributed random values).

Values are averaged out per month and are reported in the data set over the years 1961-1990. In the original paper where ANM was tested with this data set, they only tested and looked for the following 6 causal relationships:

1. *altitude* \rightarrow *temperature*
2. *altitude* \rightarrow *precipitation*
3. *longitude* \rightarrow *temperature*
4. *altitude* \rightarrow *sunshine*
5. *latitude* \rightarrow *temperature*
6. *longitude* \rightarrow *precipitation*

There are couple of interesting points to mention here. First, in the case [24], they pre-defined the couples for which the direction of connection should be determined and computed. For this thesis work,

this is not the case, as the directed edges are generated from the data and the direction is guessed once an edge is included in the skeleton of the graph. Second, they looked at the pairs separately rather than looking at the whole picture. In this thesis work, connections are not pre-defined and are guessed from the whole data matrix.

Main task associated with the above mentioned set is the detection of relations between different variables measured at different weather stations. Set is used in order to test several points. For example, as inter-connections between variables is rather clear and easily reasoned about, this allows for a straightforward experimentation of the proposed approach for finding those connections from given measurement. This will test the power of the approach in recovering local connections. Additionally, it is quite simple to include extra randomly generated variables to see if they affect the results and generate unwanted artifacts.

2.2 Medical Data

For second set of experiments, more complicated data set is used. This data set contains a total of 44 human carotid plaque specimens obtained from the Maastricht Pathology Tissue Collection (MPTC) [2]. Each sample is collected at the time of surgery and is immediately processed to prevent changes in the integrity of the specimen. From the obtained specimen, gene expression values, protein expression values and some other measures (like, lipid expression values) are gathered. For gene expression values, *transcriptomics* approach is taken.

Transcriptomics allows for genes to be interpreted ("transcribed") and this gives an information regarding how active a given gene is, how much it is used and will be translated into protein. Figure 2.1 shows a general flow of a such approach at data gathering.

Figure 2.1: Flow of Transcriptomics approach

For this thesis, only part of the available data is used. Namely, gene expression values and protein expression levels are two domains for which inter-connectional relations are studied in this thesis. Estimated connections can either lead to new hypothesis that can further advance the understanding of the underlying mechanism of human biological system or can lead to further validation of the proposed approach.

For gene expression values data set, values for 22184 genes is available over 44 human carotid plaques. As such a vast number of genes introduces several computational and validation problems (mainly, time it takes to produce the results), genes are screened and filtered based on their average expression value over all the plaques available. However, it should be noted that, for future work, whole genome should be used in the experiments.

For protein expression levels data set, measures for 1352 proteins are available over 44 plaques. Some of the measured proteins possess a known relation to a single or group of genes. Such proteins are used for the validation purposes of the obtained models. Next chapters will delve into the proposed hybrid approach.

2.3 Summary

This chapter provided the information regarding the two data sets that are used during experiments, as well as, the main task that is being solved for each case (Experimental setup and questions). For each case, dimensionality and the origin of the data sets is described. Possible problems with the given data sets is not addressed, as they will be discussed in next chapters.

3

Graphical Models and Definitions

Chapter overview: *The following chapter gives introduction to graph models, describes the terminology that will be used in the thesis and goes into detail of what chain graphs represent*

3.1 Background

A *graphical model* [15] is formally a set of distributions, satisfying a set of conditional independence relations encoded by a graph. They are widely used in order to represent and analyze not only the conditional independencies, but also the causal relationships among random variables. In [10, 27] graphical models have been described in general and have applied them in different domains. Graphical Models lie at the intersection of probability and graphs theory; they are based on a rigorous foundation and they provide a flexible and well-formalised language for modeling application domains. Bayesian Networks (BN) [35] and Markov Networks (MN) [22] are the two most well-known classes of graphical models. BNs represent the relations among random variables with directed acyclic graphs, whereas MNs represent the information as being an undirected graph. There is a key difference between the two alternatives. In BNs, a missing edge between variables means that they are conditionally independent given all other variables, whereas, in case of MNs, a missing edge means that the variables are conditionally independent given all prior variables. Figure 3.1 shows an example of a BN and an MN.

Figure 3.1: Example of a Bayesian Network (left) and Markov Network (right)

Another alternative graphical model, which has recently drawn some attention to it is Chain Graphs (CG). CGs are a class of probabilistic graphical models. CGs were first introduced by Lauritzen, Wermuth and Frydenberg in their seminal work [12, 36, 20]. One substantial difference between CG and MN/BN is that, CG allows for both directed and undirected edges with the restriction of not having directed cycles within the graph. Another example of a CG (first one being Figure 1.1) can be seen in Figure 3.2. As

mentioned earlier, what makes CGs an attractive alternative is their flexibility (in terms of being able to add data at later stages to the model) and also, a possibility of integration of clearly separated data matrices. Both of these points are relevant within the scope of this thesis, as the main interest within the scope of this thesis is the modeling of the multi *-omics* data. Chain Graphs are also appropriate especially when there are both response-explanatory and symmetric association relations among variables. This is one of the differences between BNs and MNs on one hand and CGs on the other, as BNs specifically deal with the response-explanatory relations, whereas MNs deal with symmetric association relations.

Figure 3.2: Example of a Chain Graph (without block division)

Additionally, versatility of the Chain Graphs makes an appealing approach. One of the reasons they are not very common in practice is the lack of powerful techniques or software packages that can build the model automatically from given input. This thesis work proposes a hybrid approach in order to contribute to the field and make chain graph constructions a bit more straight-forward.

3.2 Terminology

Before moving on to explaining the approach taken for chain graph construction, it is necessary to introduce some graphical model terminology. In what follows, definitions will mostly follow those in [34, 39].

A graph $G = (V, E)$ consist of a vertex set V and an edge set E . For vertices $u, v \in V$, an undirected edge $u - v$ exists if both $(u, v) \in E$ and $(v, u) \in E$. In case if $(v, u) \notin E$, but $(u, v) \in E$, then the edge between u and v is directed and is written as $u \rightarrow v$. The *skeleton* \tilde{G} of a graph G is the undirected version of a graph obtained by replacing every directed edge by an undirected edge. For skeleton graphs (equivalently, undirected graphs) a *neighborhood*, $ne_G(u)$, of a given vertex u is defined as being set of vertices v for which $u - v$ is in G .

A *route* in G is a sequence of vertices $(v_0, \dots, v_k), k \geq 0$, such that $(v_{i-1}, v_i) \in E$ or $(v_i, v_{i-1}) \in E$ for $i = 1, \dots, k$, and the vertices v_0 and v_k are called *terminals* of the route. If all the vertices that are included in the route are distinct, then the route is called a *path*. A route is called a *pseudocycle* if $v_0 = v_k$, and a *cycle* if further $k \geq 3$ and v_0, \dots, v_{k-1} are distinct.

A *section* of a route $\rho = (v_0, \dots, v_k)$ in G is a maximal undirected subroute $\sigma : v_i - \dots - v_j, 0 \leq i \leq j \leq k$ of ρ . In this case, vertices v_i and v_j are the terminals of the section σ . Furthermore, the vertex v_i is called a *head-terminal* if $i > 0$ and $v_{i-1} \rightarrow v_i$ in G and otherwise it is called a *tail-terminal*. A section σ is called a *head-to-head* section if all the terminals of a section are head-terminals. A section $\sigma : v_i - \dots - v_j$ is *hit* by a set of vertices $S \subset V$, if $v_i, \dots, v_j \cap S \neq \emptyset$.

A *complex* in G is a path (v_0, \dots, v_k) , $k \geq 2$, such that $v_0 \rightarrow v_1, v_i - v_{i+1}$ (for $i = 1, \dots, k-2$) and $v_{k-1} \leftarrow v_k$ are all in G , and no additional edge exits among vertices v_0, \dots, v_k in G . Vertices v_0 and v_k are called the *parents* of the complex and the set v_1, \dots, v_{k-1} is called the *region* of the complex. This concept was first proposed and introduced in [34].

A directed edge in a graph G is called a *complex arrow* if it belongs to a complex in G . The *pattern* of G , denoted by G^* , is the graph obtained by replacing every directed edge that is not part of any of the complex of G into undirected edge. The *moral graph* G^m of G is obtained by joining the parents of each complex with an undirected edge and then transforming every directed edge into an undirected edge.

One of the last definitions needed in order to explain both the separation trees and skeleton recovery algorithm, is the notion of *c-separation* for chain graph models. A route ρ on G is *intervented* by a subset S of V if and only if there exists a section σ of ρ such that:

- either σ is a head-to-head section with respect to ρ , and σ is outside S ; or
- σ is a non head-to-head section with respect to ρ , and σ is hit by S

The above terms lead to a following definition which will be useful in coming sections and subsections.

Definition 3.2.1. Let A, B, S be three disjoint subsets of the vertex set V of a chain graph G , such that A, B are nonempty. A and B are *c-separated* by S on G , written as $\langle A, B | S \rangle_G^{sep}$, if every route with one of its terminals in A and the other in B is intervened by S . S is also called a *c-separator* for A and B .

Below figure taken from [39], shows the terminology and definitions explained above. In Figure 3.3, there are two complexes present, namely $D \rightarrow F - E \leftarrow C$ and $F \rightarrow K \leftarrow G$. The route $\rho = (D, F, E, I, E, C)$ is intervened by an empty set since the head-to-head section $E \rightarrow I \leftarrow E$ is hit by E . On the other hand, vertices D and C are not *c-separated* by E , as the route (D, F, E, C) is not intervened by E . Figure also includes a moral graph of the chain graph. In order to obtain the moral graph, moralization procedure was applied on the chain graph as described above.

Figure 3.3: (a) an example of a chain graph, (b) and its moral graph

3.2.1 Separation Trees

Skeleton recovery algorithm, which will be explained in more detail in next section, uses a decomposition approach in order to find the connections among random variables in chain graph. In order to be able to represent these decompositions, one approach is to introduce *separation trees*. Separation trees, similar to junction trees or any graph decomposition approaches, can be seen as a mapping of a given graph to a tree which can be used in order to define the treewidth of the graph and help with the solutions of different problems. They were first introduced in [13].

Separation trees consist of collections of distinct variable sets and separators that connect different sets of distinct variables. Let $\mathbb{C} = C_1, \dots, C_k$ represent a collection of distinct, but not mutually exclusive variable sets, such that $h = 1, \dots, k, C_h \subseteq V$. Let T represent a tree, where each node of a tree corresponds to a set C_h . Two sets C_i and C_j are connected with an edge/separator $e_{ij} = C_i \cap C_j$. Additionally, removing any of the edges, or equivalently a separator, will split tree T into two subtrees, T_1 and T_2 . This is an important point to keep in mind when trying to understand separation trees. More formally, separation trees can be defined as follows:

Definition 3.2.2. A tree T with node set C is a separation tree of a graph G , if

- $\cup_{C \in \mathbb{C}} = V$, and
- for any separator S in T with V_1 and V_2 defined as above by removing S , we have $\langle V_1 \setminus S, V_2 \setminus S | S \rangle_G^{sep}$

For completeness, an example shown in previous subsection is extended here. Let

$$\mathbb{C} = \{\{A, B, C\}, \{B, C, D\}, \{C, D, E\}, \{D, E, F\}, \{E, I, J\}, \{D, F, G, H, K\}\}$$

Then, the corresponding separation tree constructed with given collection of vertex sets and chain graph from Figure 3.3, is shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Separation Tree of a chain graph from Figure 3.3, with given collection of vertex sets

As it can be seen from the picture above and overall definition of separation trees, it is clear that they represent a global information locally and are appropriate scheme for representing the decomposition of knowledge represented by a chain graph. Also, there should be a way to combine the local information into a global structure in order to generate Chain Graphs from its Separation tree. This idea is the main back-bone of the Skeleton Recovery Algorithm [39] which will be described in next chapter.

3.3 Summary

The above chapter introduced the required notion and terminology that is used throughout this thesis work. First, different graphical models and choice of specifically Chain Graphs is described. Next, the reader is introduced to the graph theoretical terminology, such as *skeleton*, *neighborhood*, *route*, *section*, *path and complex*. Definition of these terminologies is necessary for the better and easier understanding and explanation of the algorithms described in next chapter. Last, definition and logical explanation of Separation Trees, as well as, their importance in the hybrid approach is described. In short, Separation Trees represent a local decomposition of a global knowledge that a given graph contains.

Chain Graph Construction

Chapter overview: *The following chapter explains in detail the hybrid approach used for generation of chain graphs from given data sets. Overall motivation and the structural details for the approach are explained and described.*

In recent years, one field that attracted attention to it is the structural learning of the graphical models. As such, different techniques have been implemented and experimented with [39]. One thing missing in the recent literature was the complete approach of estimating the chain graphs from large data sets, especially in a sparse way. Sparsity condition becomes more relevant and necessary when field of interest is medical cases. In order to overcome this gap in literature and combine several powerful techniques together, this thesis proposes a hybrid approach for learning of chain graphs. Generic flow of the approach can be seen in Figure 4.1.

As can be seen from the figure, first couple of steps of the approach deal with the pre-processing of the data. These steps are not covered in this thesis work. In the order in which algorithms are applied, first is the creation of Undirected Independence Graph of a given data set. This is accomplished by applying **Glasso** [11] algorithm on the dataset. Glasso estimates the sparse inverse covariance matrix from a given data matrix. Inverse covariance matrix is also called a *precision matrix*, and elements of a given precision matrix represent the information about the conditional independence among variables.

After estimating the independence graph, next step is the recovery of the general structure of the chain graph. For this purpose, Skeleton Recovery of a Chain Graph Structure via Decomposition [39] is used. As an input, this method takes the junction tree obtained from the precision matrix. Junction trees in this case are equivalent to the separation trees explained in previous section.

As a final step, edges that are contained within the skeleton that connect two random variables from different domains are assigned a direction, using Additive Noise Models (ANM for short). In this thesis, usage of ANMs is appropriate as the distinction between directed and undirected edges is clear (Different knowledge domains have directed edges in-between and each knowledge domain represent a single block of a chain graph). ANMs have been shown to be an effective algorithm for causal relationship discovery in observational data [24].

As mentioned already in first chapter, one of the main issues the proposed approach should deal with, is the dimensionality problem. Previous approaches both lacked the automated nature in them, and were not directly applicable for larger cases. Proposed algorithm is made of several algorithms, all known to work well with big data sets. For example, the Glasso algorithm, uses L_1 penalty for estimation of inverse covariance matrix, in order to increase the sparsity of the obtained results. In case of large data sets, especially the medical ones, sparsity is expected and is assumed, thus making the decision of using the Glasso algorithm even stronger. Additionally, the Glasso algorithm is shown to be faster in time comparison experiments [11] when compared to its alternatives.

In case of the skeleton recovery algorithm, as far as it is known, it is one of the best alternatives that can build up a global skeleton based on a local decomposition of the knowledge. In [39], it is proven that, if graph to be estimated is of sparse nature, then, the proposed skeleton recovery algorithm is faster than its alternative, namely *Studený's Algorithm*.

Last, Additive Noise Models (ANM) are chosen as directionality recovery algorithm. Model assumptions of the thesis reduces the causal discovery problem into bivariate causal discovery problem. Reason

for this is that, underlying assumption of Chain Graphs limits the edges to be directed if and only if they connect two variables from different domains. This naturally means that causal discovery should be applied on two variables at a time, thus creating/boiling down to a bivariate causal discovery problem. ANMs are proven to be stronger predictors of causality in observational data [24], thus motivating the choice of their application in this thesis work.

Next subsections will describe each algorithm in detail in a logical order. Even though, from the overall approach perspective, Independence Graph generation comes first, logically it makes sense to give explanation of Skeleton Recovery Algorithm first, as the necessity for glasso algorithm comes more clear once Skeleton Recovery is explained. Thus, in what follows, Skeleton Recovery is explained first, then leading to the explanation of glasso algorithm and chapter ends with the description and use of ANM.

Figure 4.1: Step by step workflow of hybrid approach.

4.1 Skeleton Recovery

As discussed earlier, one of the most important parts of the hybrid approach is the creation of a skeleton of relations among variables/features of a given data set. One method to achieve this goal is introduced in [39]. Their approach makes use of graph decomposition and then learning the structure of the chain graph from the obtained/given decomposition. The algorithm is based upon a theorem (Theorem 3 in [39]) describing the conditions under which an edge between two vertices u and v should be in the skeleton G' . The theorem states that, an edge (u, v) is in the skeleton G' , if and only if $X_u \not\perp\!\!\!\perp X_v | X_S$ for any $S \subseteq V \setminus \{u, v\}$. Here, $X_u \not\perp\!\!\!\perp X_v | X_S$ means that, two variables X_u and X_v are **not conditionally independent** given the values of X_S . Therefore, learning the skeleton of a graph G reduces to just

searching for c -separators (as introduced in previous chapter) for all vertex pairs. Theorem 4.1.1 sums up all the mentioned points together.

Theorem 4.1.1. *Let T be a separation tree for a chain graph G . Then vertices u and v are c -separated by some set $S_{uv} \subset V$ in G if and only if one of the following conditions hold:*

1. u and v are not contained together in any node of T
2. u and v are contained together in some node \mathbb{C} , but for any separator S connected to \mathbb{C} , $\{u, v\} \not\subseteq S$, and there exists $S'_{uv} \subseteq \mathbb{C}$ such that $\langle u, v | S'_{uv} \rangle_G^{sep}$,
3. u and v are contained together in a node \mathbb{C} and both of them belong to some separator connected to \mathbb{C} , but there is a subset S'_{uv} of either $\cup_{u \in \mathbb{C}'} \mathbb{C}'$ such that $\langle u, v | S'_{uv} \rangle_G^{sep}$

For the proof of the above theorem, please refer to [39].

Theorem 4.1.1 shows that, given a separation tree, skeleton recovery procedure can be localized into a single node or a small subset of tree nodes (of separation tree). The whole procedure can be summarized in Algorithm 1. In its first stage, algorithm tries to construct the local connections within each node of the separation tree. By first condition of the Theorem 4.1.1, if a connection is missing in any local skeleton, then it should be excluded in global skeleton as well. Afterwards, second stage of the algorithm recovers the initial global skeleton by combining the information gathered locally. However, this initial version of the global skeleton might include extra edges. Stage three of the algorithm tries to discover those edges and remove them from the skeleton, and thus can be regarded as being a "clean-up stage".

Algorithm 1 Skeleton Recovery with a Separation Tree [39]

Input: A separation tree T of G , conditional independence knowledge.

Output: The skeleton G' of G , a set S of c -separators.

```

1: Set  $S = \emptyset$ 
2: for all Tree Node  $C_h$  do
3:   Start from a complete undirected graph  $G_h$  with vertex set  $C_h$ ;
4:   for all Vertex Pair  $\{u, v\} \subset C_h$  do
5:     if  $\exists S_{uv} \subset C_h$  s.t.  $u \perp\!\!\!\perp v | S_{uv}$  then
6:       Delete the edge  $(u, v)$  in  $G_h$ ;
7:       Add  $S_{uv}$  to  $S$ ;
8: combine the graphs  $G_h = (C_h, E_h), h = 1, \dots, k$  into an undirected graph  $G' = (V, \cup_{h=1}^k E_h)$ ;
9: for all Vertex pair  $\{u, v\}$  contained in more than one tree node and  $(u, v) \in G'$  do
10:  if  $\exists C_h$  s.t.  $\{u, v\} \subset C_h$  and  $(u, v) \notin E_h$  then
11:    Delete the edge  $(u, v)$  in  $G'$ ;
12: for all Vertex pair  $\{u, v\}$  contained in more than one tree node and  $(u, v) \in G'$  do
13:  if  $u \perp\!\!\!\perp v | S_{uv}$  for some  $S_{uv} \subset ne_{G'}(u)$  or  $ne_{G'}(v)$  such that it is not a subset of any  $C_h$  with  $\{u, v\} \subset C_h$  then
14:    Delete the edge  $(u, v)$  in  $G'$ ;
15:    Add  $S_{uv}$  to  $S$ ;

```

One of the main issues, regarding the above algorithm are its inputs. The Algorithm makes the assumption that the separation tree of the graph, as well as the conditional independence knowledge about the underlying probability distribution are available. These leads to two questions that should be answered before being able to use the above algorithm.

1. How can separation trees be constructed from observational data?
2. How can one deal with the absence of perfect conditional independence knowledge about the underlying probability distribution?

The answer to the first question is described in the next section. One approach for constructing separation trees is the approach of estimating conditional independence graph from a data using lasso regression. The **Glasso** algorithm [11] is one alternative, that estimates a sparse inverse covariance matrix. This approach has the benefit of being fast, simple and the approach tries to estimate a sparse inverse covariance matrix [11]. Sparsity is a relevant point, as many medical interactional data sets are expected/believed to be of sparse nature.

For the second question, simply hypotheses testing approach can be used in order to test the conditional independences between variables. Some issues are present with this approach, but they are discussed in later sections.

4.2 Undirected Independence Graph

As mentioned earlier, for skeleton recovery, construction of separation trees is one of the issues that has to be solved. The problem of construction of separation trees can be boiled down to estimation of *Undirected Independence Graph (UIG)* of a graph G , using the theorems from [39] and [38]. UIG of a graph G is defined as follows. A graph U is an UIG of a graph G with vertex set V , if for any $u, v \in V$,

$$(u, v) \text{ is not an edge of } U \Rightarrow u \perp\!\!\!\perp v | V \setminus \{u, v\}$$

One crucial theorem, introduced and proven in [39, 38] is the following:

Theorem 4.2.1. Let G be a chain graph. Then a junction tree constructed from any undirected independence graph of G is a separation tree for G

Considering the Theorem 4.2.1, problem of constructing separation tree switches to construction of junction tree of a UIG of a graph G . As several junction tree generation algorithms already exist [29], the whole problem of construction of separation trees reduces to estimation of UIGs. One famous approach for estimating UIGs is the **Glasso** algorithm [11]. Glasso algorithm estimates the sparse inverse covariance matrix of a given data matrix by solving a Lasso regularization problem. Next subsection goes into details of this algorithm.

4.2.1 Glasso Algorithm

For a given data set with n observations and p features, the problem of estimating its true covariance (inverse covariance) matrix, Σ , is a challenging task. Recently, there have been some work done on trying to solve this problem. One such approach is Glasso algorithm, introduced in [11]. Main assumption of Glasso algorithm is that the inverse of a covariance matrix, $\Theta = \Sigma^{-1}$, is sparse in its nature. One interesting point to mention is that, the inverse of a given covariance matrix, contains information regarding the conditional independence among variables. More concretely, if for given two variables i and j , Θ_{ij} is equal to 0, then, i and j are conditionally independent given all the other variables. Θ matrix is also called a precision matrix. In the Glasso algorithm, in order to increase the sparsity of the obtained inverse covariance matrix, L_1 penalty is imposed.

In the Glasso algorithm, following log-likelihood metric is being maximized:

$$\log(\det \Theta) - \text{tr}(S\Theta) - \rho \|\Theta\|_1 \quad (4.1)$$

In Equation 4.1, tr denotes the trace of a matrix, S is the empirical covariance matrix, ρ is the regularization parameter and $\|\Theta\|_1$ represents the entry-wise L_1 norm - the sum of the absolute values of the elements of the matrix. Equation 4.1 is the Gaussian log-likelihood of the data, maximized respect to the mean parameter μ . The Glasso algorithm applies a block coordinate descent optimization approach in order to solve the above maximization problem. Internally, instead of solving for Θ , Glasso estimates the Σ matrix and simultaneously keeps track of the corresponding Θ as well.

Let W be the estimate of Σ . Block coordinate descent approach to estimating W , first partitions the matrices W and S , as follows:

$$W = \begin{pmatrix} W_{11} & w_{12} \\ w_{12}^T & w_{22} \end{pmatrix}, S = \begin{pmatrix} s_{11} & s_{12} \\ s_{12}^T & s_{22} \end{pmatrix},$$

where W_{11} is of size $(p-1) \times (p-1)$, w_{12} is of size $(p-1) \times 1$ and w_{22} is a scalar. Θ is partitioned the same way. Initial approach, upon which glasso upgrades, shows that the solution for w_{12} satisfies

$$w_{12} = \operatorname{argmin}_y \{y^T W_{11}^{-1} y : \|y - s_{12}\|_\infty \leq \rho\} \quad (4.2)$$

The Equation 4.2 is a box-constrained quadratic program. In [5], this problem is solved by using interior point procedure. Rows and columns are repeatedly permuted, until convergence and each case is solved using the interior point algorithm. After each permutation, estimate for W is updated with new results. Through convex duality, it can be shown that [5], solving Equation 4.2 is equivalent to solving the dual problem

$$\min_{\beta} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \|W_{11}^{\frac{1}{2}} \beta - b\|_2^2 + \rho \|\beta\|_1 \right\} \quad (4.3)$$

where $b = W_{11}^{-\frac{1}{2}} s_{12}$. Equivalence between solutions can be seen by analysing the solution β . If β solves the Equation 4.3, then $w_{12} = W_{11} \beta$ solves the Equation 4.2. One thing to note here is that, Equation 4.3, resembles a lasso regression problem.

Using properties of inverse of block partitioned matrices, $W = \Theta^{-1}$ can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} W_{11} & w_{12} \\ w_{12}^T & w_{22} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (\Theta_{11} - \frac{\theta_{12}\theta_{21}}{\theta_{22}})^{-1} & -W_{11} \frac{\theta_{12}}{\theta_{22}} \\ (-W_{11} \frac{\theta_{12}}{\theta_{22}})^T & \frac{1}{\theta_{22}} - \frac{\theta_{21} W_{11} \theta_{12}}{\theta_{22}^2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Theta_{11}^{-1} + \frac{\Theta_{11}^{-1} \theta_{12} \theta_{21} \Theta_{11}^{-1}}{\theta_{22} - \theta_{21} \Theta_{11}^{-1} \theta_{12}} & -\frac{\Theta_{11}^{-1} \theta_{12}}{\theta_{22} - \theta_{21} \Theta_{11}^{-1} \theta_{12}} \\ -\frac{\Theta_{11}^{-1} \theta_{12}}{\theta_{22} - \theta_{21} \Theta_{11}^{-1} \theta_{12}} & \frac{1}{\theta_{22} - \theta_{21} \Theta_{11}^{-1} \theta_{12}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

Sub-gradient equation for maximization of Equation 4.1 is

$$W - S - \rho \times \Gamma = 0 \quad (4.5)$$

where $\Gamma_{ij} \in \operatorname{sign}(\theta_{ij})$ and W represents the derivative of $\log \det \Theta$ [31]. Now, consider the Equation 4.5 for the last column of the matrix.

$$-w_{12} + s_{12} + \lambda \gamma_{12} = 0 \quad (4.6)$$

Equivalently, w_{12} can be read from the Equation 4.4.

$$w_{12} = -W_{11} \theta_{12} / \theta_{22} \quad (4.7)$$

Combining the Equations 4.6 and 4.7, following gradient equation can be obtained:

$$W_{11} \beta + s_{12} + \lambda \gamma_{12} = 0 \quad (4.8)$$

where $\beta = \frac{\theta_{12}}{\theta_{22}}$. Equation 4.8 is the main formula on which Glasso algorithm operates. The Glasso algorithm solves the Equation 4.8, by applying coordinate descent algorithm to solve lasso regression problems. This is appropriate, as Equation 4.8, is the stationarity equation for the following l_1 regularized quadratic program:

$$\min_{\beta \in \mathbb{R}^{p-1}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \beta' W_{11} \beta + \beta' s_{12} + \lambda \|\beta\|_1 \right\} \quad (4.9)$$

Algorithm 2 summarizes the above mentioned points into a complete Glasso algorithm, as described in [11].

As it can be seen in Algorithm 2, last step requires to compute $\tilde{\theta}_{jj}$ and convert the produced results into Θ matrix. $\tilde{\theta}_{jj}$ values can be computed as follows:

$$\tilde{\theta}_{jj} = \frac{1}{w_{22} + w_{12}^T \tilde{\beta}} \quad (4.10)$$

Using the identity $W \times \Theta = I$, an equation for $\tilde{\theta}_{12}$ for a specific column can be computed using the equation below:

$$\tilde{\theta}_{12} = -W_{11}^{-1} w_{12} \theta_{22} = \tilde{\beta} \tilde{\theta}_{22} \quad (4.11)$$

Algorithm 2 Glasso Algorithm [11]

Input: Empirical covariance matrix \mathbf{S} , regularization parameter λ **Output:** Estimated covariance matrix \mathbf{W} , estimated inverse covariance matrix Θ

1. Initialize $W = S + \lambda I$
 2. Cycle around the columns repeatedly, performing the following steps till convergence:
 - (a) Rearrange the rows/columns so that the target column is last (implicitly)
 - (b) Solve the lasso problem from Equation 4.9
 - (c) Update the row/column (off-diagonal) of the covariance using \tilde{w}_{12} (Equation 4.7)
 - (d) Save $\tilde{\beta}$ for this column in the matrix \mathbf{B}
 3. Finally, for every row/column, compute the diagonal entries $\tilde{\theta}_{jj}$, and convert the \mathbf{B} matrix to Θ
-

Above mentioned formulas and updates, together make up the Glasso algorithm. An essential part of the algorithm is to get the solution to the lasso problem in step (2) of Algorithm 2. In this thesis, two approaches have been implemented in order to get solution vector at each step: 1. Proximal Gradient Algorithm, 2. Coordinate Descent. In the experiments, Proximal Gradient algorithm did not perform well and sometimes results did not convergence to a meaningful matrix. However, coordinate descent approach, originally also proposed in [11], performed as expected. In short, coordinate descent approach uses the following update form at each step. Let $V = W_{11}$ and $u = s_{12}$ for a given column k . Then, the update has the following form:

$$\tilde{\beta}_j \leftarrow S(u_j - \sum_{k \neq j} V_{kj} \tilde{\beta}_k, \rho) / V_{jj} \quad (4.12)$$

where j represents the index of an element within a β vector and not the column for which lasso problem is being solved. In Equation 4.12, S represent the soft-threshold operator:

$$S(x, t) = \text{sign}(x)(|x| - t)_+ \quad (4.13)$$

4.3 Additive Noise Models

As a last step of the hybrid approach, directions of the edges connecting variables from different domains has to be estimated. Direction of the edge represents the causal relation between variables. For example, if a random variable X changes the value of Y and affects the expression levels of Y , then this fact is represented as $X \rightarrow Y$. Causality discovery has been a major research topic for many years and has been mainly applied and researched within the fields where time-series data is available. In recent years, there have also been attempts at distinguishing cause from effect in the case of observational data. Causality discovery problem within observational data is a tricky and debatable point by itself, however, within a set of assumptions, it is a valid one.

One algorithm known to be powerful at distinguishing cause from effect is Additive Noise Models (ANM) (also, known as Additive White Gaussian Noise Models). More generically, Additive Noise Models are known as *Structural Equation Models (SEM)* [37, 7]. SEM models assume that effects are linear functions of their causes plus independent, Gaussian noise. They have been used commonly in fields like econometry, sociology and some others. Even though, mathematically speaking assumption of linearity and Gaussianity is convenient, it is not always the case and is not always true to assume so. More generic version of SEM is known as *Functional Models*, where effects are modeled as possibly nonlinear function of their cause and latent noise variable.

In this thesis, main focus is on the application of SEM or ANM models on the bivariate case. In other words, given two random variables X and Y , and the information that there should be a connection among the two, which hypothesis regarding either X causing Y or vice-versa is more likely?

In [24], it is described that, if a variable Y is a direct effect of a cause X and some latent causes $U = (U_1, \dots, U_m)$, then it is logical to model this interaction by following SEM model:

$$\begin{cases} Y = f(X, U_1, \dots, U_m), \\ X \perp\!\!\!\perp U, X \sim p_X(x), U \sim p_U(u_1, \dots, u_m) \end{cases}$$

where $f : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a possibly nonlinear function, and p_X and p_U are the joint densities of the observed cause X and latent causes U . The observational distribution corresponding to the above model is denoted by $\mathbb{P}_{X,Y}^1$. As a next step, latent causes U can be grouped into a single *noise* variable $E_Y \in \mathbb{R}$. Thus, changing the model to:

$$\begin{cases} Y = f(X, E_Y), \\ X \perp\!\!\!\perp E_Y, X \sim p_X(x), E_Y \sim p_{E_Y}(e_Y) \end{cases}$$

Similarly, construction of a noise variable can be performed in the other direction, in order to obtain a model that induces the same observational distribution. In other words, function f_X and a random variable E_X can be constructed in a following fashion:

$$\begin{cases} X = f(Y, E_X), \\ Y \perp\!\!\!\perp E_X, X \sim p_Y(y), E_X \sim p_{E_X}(e_X) \end{cases}$$

Above model induces the same observational distribution P_{XY} . However, one important fact to note there is that, in general cases, the interventional distributions obtained from the first and the second models described above will be different from the one obtained using the third model. This means that, when an observational distribution can be modeled either as described in second model or as described in third model, there is no way to identify the causal relationship between variables X and Y from just observational data without making further assumptions. This symmetry, without the access to the interventional distribution, prevents an individual from drawing conclusions regarding the direction of the causal relationship between two variables.

In order to break this symmetry, different approaches have been put forward. Main idea behind is to reduce the complexity of the model, and introduce asymmetries through reduced complexity of the models. Some of these approaches can be found in [17, 8]. In this thesis work and in [24], the asymmetry is introduced by making use of the results obtained in [26]. Hoyer showed in his paper that, nonlinearity of the functional relationship aids to the identifiability of the causal relationship, as long as the influence of the noise parameter is additive. This can be summarized within a following model [26]:

Definition 4.3.1. A tuple (p_X, p_{E_Y}, f_Y) consisting of a density p_X , a density p_{E_Y} , with finite mean, and a function $f_Y : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, defines a **bivariate Additive Noise Model (ANM)** $X \rightarrow Y$ by:

$$\begin{cases} Y = f_Y(X) + E_Y, \\ X \perp\!\!\!\perp E_Y, X \sim p_X, E_Y \sim p_{E_Y} \end{cases}$$

If the induced distribution has a density with respect to Lebesgue measure, the induced density is said to satisfy an additive noise model $X \rightarrow Y$.

The above model can be seen as a special case of a second model described in this section, where the influence of the noise is additive. In order to make use of the ANMs for guessing the causal relationship in case observational data, following lemma plays a crucial role:

Lemma 4.3.1. Given a joint density $p(x, y)$ of two random variables X, Y such that the conditional expectation $E(Y|X) = x$ is well-defined for all x , then, $p(x, y)$ satisfies a bivariate ANM $X \rightarrow Y$ if and only if $E_Y := Y - E(Y|X)$ has finite mean and is independent of X

Proof of the above lemma can be found in [24]. Above lemma allows us to apply the idea of ANMs to observational data. In order to do so, one can apply regression technique in order to find values of $E(Y|X)$, and then test for the independence between residuals and input variable. This is rather relevant, as in practice joint density function is most of the times not available and only limited amount of samples are available to make decision upon. This general procedure is summed up in Algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3 receives as input *training set* and *test set* and methods that should be used for regression and scoring function for independence tests. Training set is used in order to estimate the regression model and test set is used for testing independence of the residuals. In this thesis, *data recycling* approach is used. In *data recycling*, same data set is used as both training set and test set of the Algorithm 3.

For Algorithm 3, methods for regressing a variable X on variable Y , or vice-versa, can be chosen freely. Same is applied for the independence test. One interesting point to look into in Algorithm 3, is the decision-making stage. Overall, with the above explained approach, $X \rightarrow Y$ and $Y \rightarrow X$ models can be tested separately and based on threshold a null hypothesis can be either rejected or not. However, possible noise in measurements can turn the threshold selection process a tricky and complex one. For

that end, one way of overcoming the issue is through the means of a *priori* assumption that density distribution $p(x, y)$ satisfies an ANM $X \rightarrow Y$ or $Y \rightarrow X$ and not the both at the same time. This allows one to choose a direction of the relation based on the comparison between the test statistics gathered, using the supplied score estimator.

Algorithm 3 General procedure for deciding the direction of causal relation [24]

Input: Training Data D_N for regression, Test Data D'_N for statistical test, Regression method, Score Estimator \hat{C}

Output: Direction of the connection

1. Use the regression method to obtain estimates using the training data
 - (a) \hat{f}_Y of the regression function $x \mapsto \mathbb{E}(Y|X = x)$
 - (b) \hat{f}_X of the regression function $y \mapsto \mathbb{E}(X|Y = y)$
 2. Use the estimated regression functions in order to estimate the residuals using the test data D'_N
 - (a) $\hat{e}'_Y := y' - \hat{f}_Y(x')$
 - (b) $\hat{e}'_X := x' - \hat{f}_X(y')$
 3. Calculate the scores to measure the dependence between inputs and the residuals using test data
 - (a) $\hat{C}_{X \rightarrow Y} := \hat{C}(x', \hat{e}'_Y)$
 - (b) $\hat{C}_{Y \rightarrow X} := \hat{C}(y', \hat{e}'_X)$
 4. Return the direction of the connection based on the results obtained from score estimator. The direction with lower score \hat{C} is chosen.
-

Next subsection will discuss an alternative for score estimator required by the Algorithm 3.

4.3.1 HSIC score

One such measure for estimating the independence between an input variable and a residual is *Hilbert-Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC)* [1]. HSIC uses the sum of the squared singular values of the cross-covariance operator (its squared *Hilbert-Schmidt* norm) in order to measure dependence. Equation 4.14 represents the HSIC score for given two random variables X and Y with joint distribution $\mathbb{P}_{X,Y}$, and bounded kernels $k : \mathbb{X}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $l : \mathbb{Y}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

$$\text{HSIC}_{k,l}(X, Y) := \mathbb{E}(k(X, X')l(Y, Y')) + \mathbb{E}(k(X, X'))\mathbb{E}(l(Y, Y')) - 2\mathbb{E}(\mathbb{E}(k(X, X')|X)\mathbb{E}(l(Y, Y')|Y)) \quad (4.14)$$

, where (X, Y) and (X', Y') are two independent random variables distributed according to $\mathbb{P}_{X,Y}$.

Using the *characteristic kernel* notation introduced in [16], independence criterion justification for HSIC can be expressed as follows:

Lemma 4.3.2. Whenever the product kernel $k \cdot l$ is characteristic, $\text{HSIC}_{k,l}(X, Y) = 0$, if and only if $X \perp\!\!\!\perp Y$ (X and Y are independent)

A more in-depth explanation of characteristic kernels can be found in [4]. Examples of such kernels are Gaussian Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernels and Laplace kernels. For practical purposes, the estimator of the HSIC described below is used:

Definition 4.3.2. Given two N-tuples (with $N \leq 2$) $x = (x_1, \dots, x_N) \in X^N$ and $y = (y_1, \dots, y_N) \in Y^N$, and bounded kernels k and l , the estimator of HSIC metric is defined as

$$\widehat{\text{HSIC}}_{k,l}(x, y) := (N-1)^{-2} \text{tr}(\text{KHLH}) = (N-1)^{-2} \sum_{i,j=1}^N \tilde{K}_{ij} L_{ij} \quad (4.15)$$

where $K_{ij} = k(x_i, x_j)$, $L_{ij} = l(y_i, y_j)$ are Gram matrices, $H_{ij} = \delta_{ij} - N^{-1}$ is a centering matrix and $\tilde{K} := HKH$ is the centered Gram Matrix K . Given a finite sample drawn from a probability distribution $\mathbb{P}_{X,Y}$, empirical HSIC can be computed using the equation above.

In this thesis, as suggested in [24], Gaussian kernel is used in HSIC computations. Gaussian kernel is defined as:

$$k_{\hat{\zeta}} : (x, x') \mapsto \exp\left(-\frac{(x - x')^2}{\hat{\zeta}^2}\right)$$

In the above definition of Gaussian kernels, $\hat{\zeta}$ represent the bandwidth of the kernel. One approach for estimating bandwidth is through the means of median heuristic introduced in [32]:

$$\hat{\zeta}(u) := \text{median}\{\|u_i - u_j\| : 1 \leq i < j \leq N, \|u_i - u_j\| \neq 0\}$$

Considering that Gaussian kernels, themselves are characteristic and their product is also characteristic, then HSIC procedure using above kernels will detect any given dependence asymptotically [24].

Next chapter focuses on the use of the hybrid approach explained in this chapter.

4.4 Summary

In the chapter above, general introduction to the proposed hybrid approach is given. The approach consists of three independent stages: 1. Sparse Inverse Covariance Matrix estimation, 2. Skeleton Recovery, 3. Causal Discovery. For the first stage, *Graphical Lasso* algorithm is used for inverse covariance matrix estimation. For Skeleton Recovery stage of the hybrid approach, algorithm proposed in [39] is used. Lastly, Additive Noise Models are used in order to distinguish cause from effect in case of the availability of observational data. In the early stages of the chapter, motivation for the choices of the algorithms is also discussed.

Experiments and Results

Chapter overview: *The following chapter first describes the experimental setups performed within this thesis. Afterwards, results of the experiments are also reported in this chapter. Each result is followed up by a discussion.*

5.1 Experimental Setup

To evaluate the correctness of the hybrid approach, couple of experiments are performed. The main measure of the performance is the *recall* of the desired and known relations in-between blocks of knowledge. Experiments are performed over two data sets as mentioned earlier: Weather stations information and multi *-omics* data set. Results of the algorithms are presented in graphical form when applicable and in tabular form otherwise. For each obtained graphical model, also its sparsity level is reported.

For the case of weather stations data set, results are compared to the reported six pairs of relations that were manually tested in [24]. First, skeleton of the connections is retrieved for the full data matrix and afterwards, ANM has been applied on each of the connections in order to predict the cause/effect pairs. In order to test the robustness of the hybrid approach, random variables have been introduced in the data set. Random variables were generated uniformly, and values range from $[-1, 1]$.

For the case of the medical data set, validity of obtained model is achieved by checking for known relations. For example, a gene STAT1 directly affects and is related to protein with the same name. Initially, such gene-protein connections are examined. For genomics data set, genes have been screened/filtered, and the ones with low average expression values are filtered out. After the examination of lower-level models, based on the obtained results, model based on larger number of features will be built.

In all the cases, regularization parameter ρ for the Glasso algorithm is chosen in a cross-validation like fashion. Different values of ρ are used for generating models and for each value, its corresponding *StaRS* [14] metric is computed. This metric chooses the value for regularization parameter based on the stability of the obtained models. To do so, it estimates graphs for randomly chosen subsamples of the data set and looks at the variability across subsamples. Then, the ρ value corresponding to the optimal *StaRS* metric value is chosen as a final model. More details on *StaRS* metric and its computation can be found in [14].

All the experiments were carried on a Intel Core i7 laptop, with 8GB RAM running Windows 8.1 on a 64-bit architecture. Running times of the algorithms are mentioned when relevant.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Weather station data

In this experiment, the proposed algorithm is applied on the German Weather Stations data set. As mentioned earlier, data set contains information regarding six features measured at different weather stations over a span of 21 years (1969 - 1990). In order to test the algorithm, data matrix containing the measured values is gathered. Additionally, in order to test the robustness of the algorithm, 10 random variables have been added to the data. For these random variables, their expression levels are drawn from uniform distribution in the interval of $[0,1]$. In [24], following six pair of connections were manually analyzed by means of ANMs:

1. *altitude* \rightarrow *temperature*
2. *altitude* \rightarrow *precipitation*
3. *longitude* \rightarrow *temperature*
4. *altitude* \rightarrow *sunshine*
5. *latitude* \rightarrow *temperature*
6. *longitude* \rightarrow *precipitation*

Figure 5.1 shows the results of Glasso algorithm combined with Skeleton Recovery algorithm. Following connections are retrieved:

1. *temperature* – *altitude*
2. *altitude* – *precipitation*
3. *longitude* – *temperature*
4. *altitude* – *latitude*
5. *longitude* – *sunshine*
6. *latitude* – *sunshine*
7. *longitude* – *precipitation*
8. *latitude* – *temperature*

There are couple of things to note here already. First, as it can be seen from the plot, random variables are neither associated with any of the input variables nor within each other. This result is rather straight-forward to validate, as it logically makes sense for randomly generated variables to not have association/correlation with measured values. Second, as it can be seen from the skeleton of the graph, algorithm seems to perform on a very high level. In other words, recall rate of the manually analyzed six pairs is very high when compared to retrieved connections. Five out of the six connections are present in the retrieved skeleton as well. Only missed connections is:

1. *altitude* \rightarrow *sunshine*

Next, directionality of the connections retrieved in the skeleton are estimated by the means of ANM. As, every variable can be regarded as being a knowledge domain by itself, ANM method is applied to every edge of the skeleton. Table 5.1 summarizes the results of applying ANM.

These results are also integrated into the skeleton recovered earlier. The resulting figure is shown below.

Figure 5.3 shows the results of using built-in complex recovery of the Skeleton Recovery Algorithm. As it can be seen from the figure, not all the directions are guessed correctly and some of the directions are missing. This also shows that, including domain knowledge about when edges should be directional is beneficial.

The results obtained from the above described experiment showed the power of the hybrid approach at estimating connections within a data set.

Figure 5.2: Results of the skeleton recovery algorithm on the weather stations data

Unfortunately, the results show that, approach was not able to re-produce the local connection. There are couple of reasons that can explain the observed behavior. First, number of samples available for model estimation is rather low. Also, for some of the samples, protein expression values are not available, thus further limiting the approach. For example, in case of STAT1 protein, out of 43 plaques that were available, only 17 had measurable values, thus decreasing the power within the data set. These unmeasured cases introduce several issues for the approach. First, missing values has to be dealt in some way. For this there are two approaches that are available and are taken in this thesis: 1. Replace all the unmeasured values with a constant representing low expression value. 2. Ignore the samples for which the expression level is unmeasured. Both of these cases have their pitfalls, which lead to an unexpected at first sight behavior of the approach.

In case when the unmeasured values are replaced with a constant value representing a low expression, underlying probability distribution of the variable is corrupted. As, causal discovery and skeleton recovery relies on covariance metrics (in case of the Glasso algorithm) and regression (in case of ANM), such a "quick-fix" is actually unacceptable. Replacing values with a constant basically tells the algorithms that even though there is a change in other variables' expression values, the variable with a missing value won't react to this change in any way. Results in both Figure 5.4 and 5.5 are testimony to this fact.

In the second case, where samples with unmeasured values are simply ignored, power level of the dataset reduces even further down. For example, in case of STAT1 experiment, sample size decreased from 43 plaques to 17 an such a low sample size is not enough for statistical or causal inference. In case of APOE experiments, sample size reduced from 43 plaques to 37. On the same note, regarding the sample size, even sample size of 43 should not be enough when a model is built around multiple thousands of variables. For weather stations data set, sample size was around 349, which is a large compared to

Figure 5.3: Results of the complex recovery of the skeleton recovery algorithm on the weather stations data

medical data set, especially for the problem that the hybrid approach is trying to solve.

Another possible issue, regarding the data set is the origin of the measurement. What is meant here by this is that, plaques can be either stable or ruptured, thus affecting the expression level and possibly the expected relation between variables. All these factors lead to method not be able to detect relation between gene and protein. These data limitations and ambiguities lead to a "failure" of the approach. However, one positive is that, 3 genes related to STAT1 protein are interconnected as one component. This can be seen in Figure 5.3, where 3190133, 7050139 and 4480433 are the genes related to STAT1 protein and 16503 is the STAT1 protein.

Similar experiment is performed for APOE gene and protein. Result is shown in Figure 5.4 and overall outcome does not differ much from the case of STAT1. Number of samples is still an issue that is creating an obstacle for the approach. In Figure 5.4, 4150338 and 16968 are the vertices of interest.

Overall conclusion that can be drawn from the above experiments is that proposed hybrid approach is theoretically able to retrieve skeleton of the interactions. This fact is validated through the means of weather stations data set. In case of medical data set, lack of powerful and clean data set, leads to issues that are beyond the scope of this thesis work. Further experiments should be performed on a data set containing more samples and where quality of the measurements is of higher level (Not too many missing values). Considering the presence of above mentioned issues within the data set, larger scale model that was obtained is omitted from this thesis.

Figure 5.4: Resulting skeleton for STAT1

5.3 Summary

Different experimental setups and results are discussed in this chapter. Results obtained on a Weather Stations data set showed the power of the proposed hybrid approach. In the case of medical data set, however, results obtained were of a lower power, as some issues were present regarding the input data matrix. Especially the low dimensionality/sample size of the data hurts the hybrid approach the most. On the other hand, even with a small sample size, algorithm managed to correctly separate the groups (Figure 5.4, STAT1 case). This showed the huge potential of success using the proposed algorithm.

Figure 5.5: Resulting skeleton for APOE

6

Conclusion and Future Work

Chapter overview: *This chapter provides a conclusion of the thesis. The research questions and problem statement described in the first chapter are addressed based on the discussions in the other chapters. Ideas for future research are discussed at the end of this chapter.*

6.1 Research Questions

This section discusses the research questions described in Section 1.3 using the findings described in previous chapter.

1. *How accurate is the skeleton recovery algorithm when combined with different approaches?*

In the structural learning, the main focus should not be only the sparsity of the obtained model but also how accurate and relevant it is. To that end, validation and verification of the models using domain knowledge is important. The Skeleton recovery algorithm by itself has shown to perform well [39]. One of the most important ideas the algorithm relies on is the separation tree that the algorithm receives as an input. Experimental study on Weather Stations data set showed that, when combined with the Glasso algorithm which estimates the sparse inverse covariance matrix of the given data set, skeleton recovery algorithm performs on a very high level and manages to retrieve the relevant edges of the skeleton. Even the addition of random variables to the data set did not affect the whole procedure and did not introduce any artifacts in the estimated graph.

2. *How different are the models obtained from stand-alone Skeleton Recovery Algorithm and Additive Noise Model (ANM) combined model?*

The Skeleton Recovery algorithm as described in [39] also provides a method that can predict which edges should be directional and in which direction they should be. One thing to mention here is that, this approach does not incorporate any domain knowledge. For example, in medical case it is known that connections from one *-omics* block to another should be directional. In case of weather stations, it can be hypothesized that every direction should be directional if there is an edge connection two variables. Comparison of two graphs is only applicable for the case of non-medical data sets, for the reasons explained in previous chapter. It can be seen from the results that built-in complex recovery does not always retrieve the directional edges completely. However, for the retrieved ones directionalities are all correct based on the ground truth of connections. In general, both approaches can be used in order to recover the directed edges, but ANMs seem more appropriate within the domain of interest for this thesis.

3. *How well does ANM predict the directions of the edges when combined with Skeleton Recovery Algorithm?*

Considering that, one of the main setbacks of the ANM approach discussed in this thesis is its bivariate nature, Skeleton Recovery Algorithm resolves that issue in an efficient way. In terms of accuracy, experiments showed that ANMs distinguish the effect from cause quite efficiently. In weather stations data set, out of the 8 edges on which ANM was tested, only one did not match with the expected directionality. This led to an 87.5% accuracy on that case. Power of ANMs on medical data set was not tested as the results from Skeleton Recovery Algorithm were not sufficient and fitting for further experimentations.

6.2 Problem Statement

The problem statement of the thesis was formulated as follows:

How can Chain Graphs be made easily applicable in multi-omics integration projects?

A hybrid approach trying to estimate the CG structure from given data set is proposed. This approach showed a powerful result on proposed non-medical data set. It is reasonable to expect that algorithm will perform well on the medical cases, if the sample size and measurement non-availability issues are resolved. Additionally, the correctness from an intuitive point of view, of the model obtained in first experiments, showed the possibility of further use of the proposed approach. Further ideas for more thorough validation and possible optimization of the approach are presented in next section.

6.3 Future Work

One possible approach to further validate the algorithm is to run it on different data sets, where causal relations are clearly indicated. One such example can be the benchmark data set introduced in [24]. Experiments on such a benchmark could further prove the usability of the hybrid approach. One big question still to be answered is the applicability of the approach on medical cases. For this, a more detailed and larger data set should be gathered. As the required data set is of special structure and complexity, it can not be found easily anywhere.

From the methodological perspective, Glasso algorithm can be replaced by the DP-Glasso [28]. Main difference between two algorithms is the function for which they are trying to solve the problem. In case of DP-Glasso algorithm, main focus is on the primal problem, rather than being on the dual solved by the Glasso algorithm. DP-Glasso algorithm solves the problem directly for inverse covariance matrix, rather than doing it so for the covariance matrix and keeping track of the estimated inverse covariance matrix, which is the case for the Glasso algorithm.

Additionally, one important aspect that can be addressed in future work is the hypothesis testing part of the Skeleton Recovery Algorithm. An alternative to the hypothesis testing can be, Bayesian statistics [30]. Most of the software packages, as well as the Skeleton Recovery algorithm uses Frequentist approaches and hypothesis testing. Although it is well known in statistics that association and significance are distinct concepts, mainly the latter has been used for dealing with term enrichment analysis. Bayesian statistics uses statistical association in parallel to significance [30].

Bibliography

- [1] A. Smola A. Gretton O. Bousquet. “Measuring statistical dependence with Hilbert-Schmidt norms”. In: *Algorithmic Learning Theory* (2005), pp. 63–78.
- [2] Pieter Goossens et. al. “Myeloid Type I Interferon Signaling Promotes Atherosclerosis by Stimulating Macrophage Recruitment to Lesions”. In: *Cell Metabolism* (2010).
- [3] P Anderson. “More is different”. In: *Science* 177 (1972), pp. 393–396.
- [4] A. Gretton et. al B. Sriperumbudur. “Hilbert space embeddings and metrics on probability measures”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* (2010), pp. 1517–1561.
- [5] Ghaoui L. Banerjee O. “Model selection through sparse maximum likelihood estimation”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* (2007).
- [6] Matteo Bersanelli et al. “Methods for the integration of multi-omics data: mathematical aspects”. In: *BMC Bioinformatics* 17.2 (2016), pp. 167–177.
- [7] K. A. Bollen. “Structural Equations with Latent Variables”. In: *John Wiley and Sons* (1989).
- [8] P. Hoyer et. al D. Janzing. “Telling cause from effect based on high-dimensional observations”. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning* (2010), pp. 479–486.
- [9] C. Di Serio and P Vicard. “Graphical Chain models for the analysis of complex genetic diseases: an application to hypertension”. In: *Statistical Modeling* (2005), pp. 119–143.
- [10] D. Edwards. “Introduction to Graphical Modeling”. In: *Springer-Verlag* (2000).
- [11] Jerome Friedman, Trevor Hastie, and Robert Tibshirani. “Sparse inverse covariance estimation with the graphical lasso”. In: *Biostatistics* 9.3 (2008), pp. 432–441. DOI: 10.1093/biostatistics/kxm045. eprint: <http://biostatistics.oxfordjournals.org/content/9/3/432.full.pdf+html>. URL: <http://biostatistics.oxfordjournals.org/content/9/3/432.abstract>.
- [12] M. Frydenberg. “The chain graph Markov property”. In: *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics* (1990), pp. 333–353.
- [13] Rudolf Halin. “S-functions for graphs”. In: *Journal of Geometry* 8 (1976), pp. 171–186.
- [14] Kathryn Roeder Han Liu and Larry Wasserman. “Stability Approach to Regularization Selection (StARS) for High Dimensional Graphical Models”. In: *Arxiv* (2010). URL: arxiv.org/pdf/1006.3316.pdf.
- [15] Michael I. Jordan. “An introduction to Graphical Models”. In: *Center For Biological and Computational Learning, MIT* (1997).
- [16] X. Sun K. Fukumizu A. Gretton. “Kernel Measures of conditional dependence”. In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 20* (2008).
- [17] Y. Kano and S. Shimizu. “Causal inference using nonnormality”. In: *Proceedings of the International Symposium on Science of Modeling, the 30th Anniversary of the Information Criterion* (2003), pp. 261–270.
- [18] H Kitano. “Systems biology: a brief overview”. In: *Science* 295.5560 (2002), pp. 1662–1664.
- [19] Peter Langfelder and Steve Horvath. “WGCNA: an R package for weighted correlation network analysis”. In: *BMC Bioinformatics* 9.1 (2008), pp. 1–13.
- [20] S. L. Lauritzen and Wermuth N. “Graphical models for associations between variables, some of which are qualitative and some quantitative.” In: *The Annals of Statistics* (1989), pp. 31–57.

- [21] Steffen L. Lauritzen and Thomas S. Richardson. “Chain Graph models and their causal interpretations”. In: *Journal of Royal Statistical Society* 64 (3 2002), pp. 321–348.
- [22] Pedro Domingos Matthew Richardson. “Markov Logic Networks”. In: *Personal Archive at University of Washington* (2008).
- [23] C McCarter and K. Seyoung. “On Sparse Gaussian Chain Graph Models”. In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (2014).
- [24] Joris M. Mooij et al. “Distinguishing Cause from Effect Using Observational Data: Methods and Benchmarks”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 17.32 (2016), pp. 1–102. URL: <http://jmlr.org/papers/v17/14-518.html>.
- [25] Kevin Murphy and Saira Mian. *Modelling gene expression data using dynamic bayesian networks*. Tech. rep. 1999.
- [26] D. Janzing et. al P. O. Hoyer. “Nonlinear causal discovery with additive noise models”. In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* (2009).
- [27] J. Pearl. “Probabilistic Reasoning in Intelligent Systems: Networks of Plausible Inference”. In: *Morgan Kaufmann* (1988).
- [28] Trevor Hastie Rahul Mazumder. “The Graphical Lasso: New Insights and Alternatives”. In: *arXiv.org* (2012).
- [29] S. L. Lauritzen R.G.Cowell A. P. Dawid and D. J. Spiegelhalter. “Probabilistic Networks and Expert Systems”. In: *Springer-Verlag, New York* (1999).
- [30] Tie Koide et. al Ricardo Z.N. Vencio. “BayGO: Bayesian analysis of ontology term enrichment in microarray data”. In: *BMC Bioinformatics* 7:86 (2006).
- [31] Boyd S. and Vandenberghe L. “Convex optimization”. In: *Cambridge University Press* (2004).
- [32] B. Scholkopf and A. Smola. “Learning with Kernels”. In: *MIT Press* (2002).
- [33] Philipp N. Spahn et al. “A Markov chain model for N linked protein glycosylation : towards a low-parameter tool for model-driven glycoengineering”. In: *Metabolic Engineering* 33 (2016), pp. 52–66. ISSN: 1096-7176. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ymben.2015.10.007>. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1096717615001354>.
- [34] M. Studeny. “A recovery algorithm for chain graphs”. In: *International Journal of Approx. Reasoning* 17 (1997), pp. 265–293.
- [35] Bayesian Networks without Tears. “Eugene Charniak”. In: *AI Magazine* 12 (1991).
- [36] N Wermuth and S. L Lauritzen. “On substantive research hypotheses, conditional independence graphs and graphical chain models”. In: *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society* (1990), pp. 21–50.
- [37] S. Wright. “Correlation and causation”. In: *Journal of Agricultural Research* (1921), pp. 557–585.
- [38] Z. Gheng X. Xie and Q. Zhao. “Decomposition of structural learning about directed acyclic graphs”. In: *Artificial Intelligence* 170 (2006), pp. 442–439.
- [39] Zhi Geng Zongming Ma Xianchao Xie. “Structural Learning of Chain Graphs via Decomposition”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning* 9 (2008), pp. 2847–2880.